

Introduction

In March 2024, during the [Open Science Retreat](#) in Schoorl, NL, participants came together to discuss a new 'Narrative for sustainable Open Access'. This resulted in the following Call to Commitment. As of the first week of January 2025, the petition **Call to Commitment: A Future-Proof Approach to Open Access Publishing in The Netherlands** has over 400 signatories from a broad range of institutions. These include all 14 Dutch universities, all 7 Dutch university medical centers, 10 universities of applied sciences and numerous other scientific and cultural institutions. The petition will remain open in the coming months.

The petition and the list of the 408 first signatories are hereby shared with the UKB Consortium, the partnership of the Dutch University Libraries and the National Library of the Netherlands (KB), and the Universities of the Netherlands and SURF who negotiate jointly with national and international publishers about licences for digital information sources.

WE NEED A FUTURE-PROOF APPROACH TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING IN THE NETHERLANDS

Sign the petition!

#1
The existing transformative deals with publishers are simply not transformative

WE NEED A FUTURE-PROOF APPROACH TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING IN THE NETHERLANDS

Sign the petition!

#2
Open science principles should be key to all deals between institutions and publishers

WE NEED A FUTURE-PROOF APPROACH TO OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING IN THE NETHERLANDS

Sign the petition!

#3
Investments should be re-directed towards community-driven Open Access

Call to Commitment: A future-proof approach to Open Access Publishing in the Netherlands

There is a growing awareness of the ways in which transformative¹ agreements between the Dutch Universities and academic publishing companies fail to increase the sovereignty of researchers at Dutch Universities² and equitable access to scientific research outputs³. The current Dutch strategy, focused on Open Access (OA) that is for-profit APC⁴-driven, has been unable to pursue community-driven publishing strategies. Therefore, we call for an alternative publishing strategy based on community values and Open Science (OS) principles.

In early 2022, the UKB consortium⁵ renewed a number of 'read and publish' contracts with key publishers that were initially established in 2015. In the coming period, a lot of these contracts are to be renegotiated and renewed⁶.

We, the undersigned, urge our respective institutions and national stakeholders, when negotiating the renewal of these contracts, to uphold the community values and OS principles to which they have previously committed themselves^{7,8}. Preferably, these values and principles are the premise of guidelines for OA negotiations, as is becoming more prevalent in Europe and beyond⁹.

Only when we put these values and principles at the forefront, can we foster a system of knowledge creation, dissemination and (re)use that is inclusive, equitable and transparent, thereby strengthening our international reputation, financial sustainability, and institutional sovereignty.

For us, this entails moving away from a mere focus on for-profit and non-inclusive models, towards a landscape that fully includes institute- and community-driven OA.

To provide these alternatives with a fair chance to demonstrate their potential, it is crucial to redirect a significant portion of the investments —currently allocated to transformative agreements— toward open-source institutional repositories, diamond platforms, preprint servers, innovations in community peer reviewing, and thematic curation that allows relevant audiences to easily access our research outputs.

Investing in these solutions will bring the Dutch research environment towards a future driven by the values that we uphold.

Footnotes

1 [Transformative agreements](#) are those contracts negotiated between institutions and publishers that aimed to transform the business model underlying scholarly journal publishing ↵

2 Safeguarding Dutch Universities Against Big Tech Dominance: Risks and mitigations

https://communities.surf.nl/files/Artikel/download/Safeguarding_Dutch_Universities_Against_Big_Tech_Dominance_0.pdf ↵

3 See eg. cOAlitionS Towards Responsible publishing https://www.coalition-s.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Towards_Responsible_Publishing_web.pdf and UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

<https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546> ↵

4 APC stands for [Article Processing Charge](#). Also known as a publication fee, it is a fee charged to authors to publish their articles open

access. Some journals charge APCs that only cover the real costs of publishing. However, most of the publishers in the current

transformative deals charge higher APCs, that also cover (large) profit margins. Therefore, APCs can range from 300 euros to over 10.000

euros for some prestige journals. ↵

5 The [UKB Consortium](#) is a partnership of the Dutch University Libraries and the National Library of the Netherlands (KB) ↵

6 List of Publishers Deals in NL <https://www.openaccess.nl/en/in-the-netherlands/publisher-deals> ↵

7 See the National Covenant Open Science NL <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/regieorgaan-open-science-officially-launched-open-science-nl> and the NPOS Ambition Document <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767> ↵

8 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546> ↵

9 Like for instance the Swiss universities, Sweden and MIT:

https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Hochschulpolitik/Open_Science/PgB_OpenScience_-_Implementation_Phase_A_2021-2024_v6.4.pdf, <https://suhf.se/app/uploads/2023/10/Charting-Swedens-path-beyond-transformative-agreements-%E2%80%93-analysis-and-proposals-for-strategic-direction-October-2023.pdf>, <https://libraries.mit.edu/scholarly/publishing/framework/> ↵

List of signatories (January 2025)

- 1 Anna van 't Veer, Leiden University & OSC-NL
- 2 Maura Cassidy Burke, Utrecht University
- 3 Loek Brinkman, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
- 4 Rashmi Shetty, Utrecht University
- 5 Ewa Miedzobrodzka, Utrecht University
- 6 Alexandra Sarafoglou, University of Amsterdam
- 7 Rianne Fijten, Maastricht University, MUMC+
- 8 Anne van den Maagdenberg, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- 9 Johan Rooryck, cOAlition S, Glossa, Leiden University
- 10 João Guimarães, Delft University of Technology
- 11 Raul Inzaurre, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
- 12 Daniel Lakens, Eindhoven University of Technology
- 13 André Brasil, CTWS, Leiden University
- 14 Frank Miedema, Utrecht University, UMC Utrecht
- 15 Katie Corker, ASAPbio
- 16 Vera Sarkol, CWI
- 17 Jean-Sébastien Caux, University of Amsterdam, SciPost
- 18 Tanya Yankelevich, Delft University of Technology
- 19 Anonymous, Amsterdam UMC
- 20 Eiko Fried, Leiden University
- 21 Nicole Emmenegger, tDCC Social Sciences and Humanities
- 22 Serge P.J.M. Horbach, Radboud University
- 23 Frédérique Belliard, Delft University of Technology Library
- 24 Anonymous
- 25 Niels Stern, OAPEN Foundation
- 26 Daniela Gawehns, UMC Groningen
- 27 Florian Schuberth, University of Twente
- 28 Mar Barrantes-Cepas, Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- 29 Thomas Pronk, Amsterdam UMC
- 30 Michèle Nuijten, Tilburg University
- 31 Melanie Imming, Imming Impact
- 32 Antonio Schettino, Erasmus University Rotterdam
- 33 Maria E. Constantin, Erasmus University Rotterdam
- 34 Marcel Haas, Leiden University Medical Center
- 35 Noah van Dongen, University of Amsterdam
- 36 Raul Zurita-Milla, University of Twente
- 37 Sarahanne M. Field, University of Groningen
- 38 Julia Cramer, Leiden University, Young Academy Leiden
- 39 Lucas C. Breedt, Amsterdam UMC
- 40 Eva van Heese, Amsterdam UMC
- 41 Louise Bezuidenhout, Leiden University
- 42 Eva Koderman, Amsterdam UMC
- 43 Tanya van Goch, SURF
- 44 Niels Reijner, Amsterdam UMC
- 45 Eduarda Centeno, Amsterdam UMC
- 46 Anonymous

47 Taichi Ochi, University of Groningen, Open Science Community Groningen
48 Margaret Gold, Leiden University
49 Susanne van Rijn, UKB, Erasmus University Rotterdam
50 Barend Mons, Leiden University
51 Tessa de Roo, Leiden University Libraries and LUMC
52 Sanne Willems, Leiden University
53 Don van Ravenzwaaij, University of Groningen
54 Femmy Admiraal, Leiden University Libraries
55 Anne Scheel, Utrecht University
56 Katharina Krüsselmann, Leiden University
57 Chris Hartgerink, Liberate Science GmbH
58 Flavio Azevedo, Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT)
59 Richard Grimes, Delft University of Technology
60 Anonymous, Utrecht University
61 Ron Hol, KB › National Library of the Netherlands
62 Louise Otting, Delft University of Technology
63 Dietsje Jolles, Leiden University
64 Egon Willighagen, Maastricht University
65 Anonymous, University of Amsterdam
66 Esther Plomp, Delft University of Technology
67 Anonymous, Leiden University Libraries
68 Marijn van 't Veer, University of Amsterdam
69 Laurens Witter, UMC Utrecht
70 Anonymous, University of Amsterdam
71 Ana Parrón Cabañero, CWTS, Leiden University
72 Naomi Truan, Leiden University
73 Mishko Bozhinoski, University of Ghent
74 Anonymous, Delft University of Technology
75 Bjørn Peare Bartholdy, Leiden University, Delft University of Technology
76 Anne Urai, Leiden University
77 Deepak Tunuguntla, Saxion University of Applied Science
78 Z. Sjoerds, Leiden University
79 Ileana Grama, University of Amsterdam
80 L. Breemer, Leiden University
81 Martijn Kingma, Universiteit van Amsterdam & Fryske Akademy
82 Rene Bekkers, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
83 Ronald Snijder, OAPEN Foundation
84 Sarah de Rijcke, Leiden University
85 Anonymous, University of Amsterdam
86 Caspar van Lissa, Open Science Community Tilburg
87 Philippa Johnson, Leiden University
88 Theo de Nooij, KB › National Library of the Netherlands
89 Charlotte Rönnau, Leiden University
90 Juan Claramunt, Leiden University
91 Willem Scholten, Erasmus University Rotterdam
92 Rüya G. Koçer, Leiden University
93 Anne Marie Meijer, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
94 Julian Karch, Leiden University

- 95 Anonymous, Leiden University
- 96 Benjamin Storme, Leiden University
- 97 Niklas Hohmann, Utrecht University
- 98 Cristina Del Real, Leiden University
- 99 Bogdana Huma, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- 100 Eva Michaels, Leiden University
- 101 James Louis Smith, Leiden University
- 102 Olaf Janssen, KB › national library of the Netherlands
- 103 Marieke Liem, Leiden University
- 104 Anonymous
- 105 Sarah Carthy, Leiden University
- 106 Bastián González-Bustamante, Leiden University
- 107 Anonymous, Utrecht University
- 108 David Kühling-Romero, Leiden University
- 109 Sara Perlstein, Leiden University
- 110 Natalia Rivera-Vera, Utrecht University/University of Amsterdam
- 111 Xinyan Fan, Delft University of Technology
- 112 Djoerd Hiemstra, Radboud University
- 113 Willemijn Plomp, Leiden University
- 114 Dennie Hebels, Maastricht University
- 115 Carlo Schuengel, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- 116 Hanneke Hulst, Leiden University
- 117 Dmitry Kochetkov, Leiden University
- 118 Bryan Lougheed, Uppsala University
- 119 Peter Bos, Leiden University
- 120 Marijke ten Brinke, NIOO-KNAW
- 121 Aad Blok, International Institute of Social History
- 122 Femke Reidsma, Leiden University
- 123 Nami Sunami, Eindhoven University of Technology
- 124 Anonymous
- 125 Alice Flerackers, University of Amsterdam
- 126 Brittany N. Ikner, Wayne State University
- 127 Anonymous
- 128 Anonymous, Erasmus MC
- 129 Johannes Lehmann, UMC Utrecht
- 130 Jaap-Henk Hoepman, Radboud University
- 131 Moritz Negwer, Radboudumc Nijmegen
- 132 Dorien Huijser, Utrecht University
- 133 Alex Rushforth, Leiden University
- 134 Jeroen Bosman, Utrecht University Library
- 135 Rebecca Hewett, Erasmus University Rotterdam
- 136 Armel Lefebvre, Leiden University
- 137 Ronald Visser, Saxion University of Applied Sciences
- 138 Anonymous
- 139 Anikó Lovik, Leiden University
- 140 Birke Benedikter, Maastricht University
- 141 Andres Ramos, RIVM
- 142 Yu Fang Yang, Freie Universität Berlin

143 Marlon Domingus, Erasmus University Rotterdam
144 Lotte van Dillen, Leiden University
145 Monika Barget, Maastricht University
146 Maximiliano Cenci, Radboudumc
147 Roman Briker, Maastricht University
148 Mutaleni Nadimi, Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision
149 Anonymous, KB › National Library of the Netherlands
150 Maša Galič, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
151 Sanne Steens, Maastricht University
152 Barbara Vermaas, Fontys University of Applied Sciences
153 Anonymous
154 Isabel Beirigo, Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision
155 Jacqueline Zadelaar, Leiden University
156 Anita Eerland, Radboud University
157 Oscar Koeroo, independent
158 Tom Barbereau, TNO
159 Johan van der Knijff, KB › national library of the Netherlands
160 J. Hadaschik, Maastricht University
161 Anonymous
162 Mathieu Paapst, University of Groningen
163 Scott Jacques, CrimRxiv Consortium
164 Monique Grenier, University of Victoria
165 Davide Nardi, Eindhoven University of Technology
166 Anonymous
167 Ad Notten, Maastricht University
168 Michel de Gruijter, KB › National Library of the Netherlands
169 Dirk van Gorp, Radboud University
170 Julia Menon, Utrecht University
171 Anonymous
172 Richard de Waard, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
173 H. Vriend, independent
174 Bonne van Dijk, independent
175 Liz Guzman Ramirez, Eindhoven University of Technology
176 Anonymous
177 Sam Nooij, Leiden University Medical Center
178 Eduard de Jong, semi-retired
179 Angela Aleksovska, Eindhoven University of Technology
180 Anonymous, KB › national library of the Netherlands
181 Katie Hudson, Leiden University
182 Lucia Forrova, Eindhoven University of Technology
183 Steven Verheyen, Erasmus University Rotterdam
184 Silvie van Dam, Eindhoven University of Technology
185 Sarah Coombs, Saxion University of Applied Sciences, DCC-PO
186 Gerben ter Riet, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, Amsterdam UMC
187 Anonymous
188 Christine Hedde-von Westernhagen, Eindhoven University of Technology
189 Wolfgang Kaltenbrunner, Leiden University
190 Jochem Zijderwijk, Radboud University Nijmegen

191 Jan Melissen, Leiden University, University of Antwerp
192 Ingrid van Gorkum, NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences
193 Barbara Malheiros, Eindhoven University of Technology
194 Luca Cerina, Eindhoven University of Technology
195 Bert N. Bakker, University of Amsterdam
196 Mira Stanic, TDCC-NES
197 Anonymous, Eindhoven University of Technology
198 Pepe Vera Campello, corporate user
199 Christopher Steven Marcum, independent
200 Jörg Henseler, University of Twente
201 Xi Yu, University of Twente
202 Anonymous
203 Michel Saive, Maastricht University
204 Dan Rudmann, Utrecht University
205 Eveline van Zeeland, University of Twente
206 Maaïke Verburg, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
207 Leo de Lange
208 Harm Veling, Wageningen University and Research
209 Mercedes Almela Zamorano, Tilburg University
210 Leander van der Meij, Eindhoven University of Technology
211 Beatriz Barrocas Ferreira, Tilburg University
212 Marian Beekman, Leiden UMC
213 Marjolein Nieboer, Rijksuniversiteit Groningen
214 Anonymous
215 Armagan Karahanoglu, University of Twente
216 René van Horik, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
217 Anonymous, University of Amsterdam
218 Wouter Grouve, University of Twente
219 Sible Andringa, University of Amsterdam
220 Rachel Plak, Leiden University
221 Lars Eijssen, Maastricht University
222 Peter Reniers, Open Universiteit
223 Ben Excell, Wageningen University & Research
224 Arent Kievits, Delft University of Technology
225 Frank Ostermann, University of Twente
226 Salomé Sanchez, University of Twente
227 Björn Brembs, Universität Regensburg, Germany
228 Stuart Cooper – ScienceOpen GmbH
229 Anonymous, Thematic Digital Competence Centre Social Sciences and Humanities
230 Leen Liefsoens, Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences
231 Ruud Steltenpool, Saxion UAS, OSC-Twente, DCC-PO
232 Paola Galimberti, University of Milan
233 Anonymous
234 Eliana Vassena, Radboud University
235 Neda Norouzi, Eindhoven University of Technology
236 John Mills, Erasmus University Rotterdam
237 Asier Moneva, Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement
238 Simon Belgers, Eindhoven University of Technology
239 Anonymous

240 Julian Lopez Gordillo, Naturalis Biodiversity Center
241 Stijn Ruiters, Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement
242 Beate Volker, Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement
243 Susaiyah, Eindhoven University of Technology
244 Danielle Stibbe, Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement
245 Janina Schaumann, University of Twente
246 Afreen Khalid, Radboud University
247 Giulia Trentacosti, University of Groningen
248 Simon Bothof, Vrije Universiteit Brussels
249 Marta Kargól, The Hague University of Applied Sciences
250 Antoinette Beumer, Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences
251 Andrea Tarchi, Erasmus University Rotterdam
252 Anonymous, Hogeschool Van Hall Larenstein
253 Anonymous, Leiden UMC
254 Lucas Baudouin, Amsterdam UMC
255 Leila Gharavi, Delft University of Technology
256 Juliana Costa Pitanguy, Delft University of Technology
257 Joana Cook, Leiden University
258 Leticia Micheli, Leiden University
259 John Boy, Leiden University
260 Myrte Vos, Leiden University
261 Sjoerd Huisman, Leiden University
262 Jon Verriet, Netherlands Commission for UNESCO
263 Nicola Thome, Leiden University
264 Anthony Thornton, University of Twente
265 Anonymous, Leiden University
266 Robyn Mooney, Maastricht University
267 Anonymous
268 Ana Barbosa Mendes, Erasmus University, Promovendi Netwerk Nederland
269 Mariëlle Prevo, Maastricht University
270 Ymke Bresser, Leiden University
271 Margreet Nieborg, University of Groningen Press
272 Sauro Civitillo, Utrecht University
273 Anonymous, Amsterdam UMC
274 Jeroen Rombouts, Erasmus University Rotterdam
275 F. Halfwerk, University of Twente
276 Ricarda Braukmann, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
277 Simon Saldner, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
278 Anthony Brown, Leiden University
279 Rita Azevedo, Lygature
280 Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Delft University of Technology
281 Anonymous, Utrecht University
282 Gerald Wildenbeest, Saxion, OSC-Twente
283 Jellie Visser, NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences
284 Maria Valdez, NIOD-NAW
285 Anonymous
286 Vera E. Heininga, University of Groningen
287 Ana Martinovici, Erasmus University
288 Anonymous

289 Anton Lebed, independent
290 Zafer Ozturk, University of Twente
291 Anonymous, Maastrou
292 Anonymous, Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience
293 Aleksandra Wilczynska, 4TU.ResearchData
294 Alice Stuart-Lee, SURF
295 Youp Hendriks, Maastricht University
296 Sabine van der Ham, Hanze Groningen
297 Joanne Yeomans, Thematic DCC-NES
298 Anonymous
299 Jose Lozano Torres, Wageningen University and Research
300 D. Vestdijk, Utrecht University of Applied Sciences
301 Yasemin Turkyilmaz, Delft University of Technology
302 Matti Vuorre, Tilburg University
303 Mats Koeneman, Radboud UMC
304 Anonymous, HAS Green Academy
305 Anonymous
306 Dominiek Smit, Maastricht University
307 Laurents Sesink, SURF
308 Jolien Scholten, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
309 Anouk Bouma, Tilburg University
310 Eileen Waegemaekers, SURF
311 Geert van Kollenburg, Eindhoven University of Technology
312 Patrick Eneche, University of Twente
313 Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Radboud UMC
314 Thed van Leeuwen, Leiden University
315 Bregt Lameris, Open University
316 Siem Jacobs, University of Twente
317 Pablo I. Ampuero-Ruiz, Leiden University
318 Daan Rutten, Tilburg University
319 BJ Bakker, MSc student
320 Lilli Zeven, Leiden University
321 Leon van Ekeren, DCC-PO
322 Burçin Yılmaz, Technical University Eindhoven
323 Marjan van Ittersum, Groningen University
324 Anonymous
325 Vincent Niochet, Leiden University
326 Florian Helmecke, Leiden University
327 Anonymous
328 Sharon van Geldere, Leiden University
329 Lars Dorren, Leiden University
330 Allard de Graaf, Leiden University
331 Anonymous, Leiden university
332 Bart Verhoeven, Maastricht University
333 Anonymous
334 Rebecca Schaefer, Leiden University
335 Robyn Cremin Leiden University
336 Niels van Doesum, Leiden University
337 Esther Tijchon, Radboud University

338 Satu Koivusaari, Leiden University
339 Henriët van Middendorp, Leiden University
340 Soohong Eum, Leiden University
341 Antoinette van Laarhoven, Leiden University
342 Julie Hall, Leiden University
343 Anonymous, Wageningen University and Research
344 Ricarda Proppert, Leiden University
345 Ineke Wessel, Groningen University
346 Kaya Peerdeman, Leiden University
347 Anonymous, Groningen University
348 Andrea Evers, Leiden University
349 Sanne van Luenen, Leiden University
350 Léonie de Jonge, Groningen University
351 Toon Kuppens, Groningen University
352 Anonymous, Leiden University
353 Antia Wiersma, Huygens KNAW
354 Anonymous, Leiden University
355 Laura Bringmann, Groningen University
356 Anna Langener, Dartmouth College
357 Yong Zhang, Groningen University
358 Pui Hang Wong, Maastricht University
359 Anonymous, Maastricht University
360 Barbara Konjevod, Tilburg University
361 Martijn Starmans, Erasmus UMC
362 Rink Hoekstra, Groningen University
363 Anne Haisma, Hanze University of Applied Sciences
364 Anonymous, Institute of Tropical Medicine BE
365 Vincent Traag, Leiden University
366 Alaa Aldoh, University of Amsterdam
367 Anonymous
368 Anonymous
369 Veronika Cheplygina, University of Copenhagen
370 Anonymous, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
371 Alie Mud, NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences
372 Daan Ornée, University of Applied Sciences Utrecht
373 Poulami Dasgupta, Maastricht University, MUMC+
374 Anonymous
375 Tessa Lobbes, BMGN – Low Countries Historical Review
376 Ionica Smeets, Leiden University
377 Sicco de Knecht, National Center of Expertise on Science
378 Marijke Naezer, independent researcher
379 Anonymous
380 Gisela van der Velden, UMC Utrecht
381 Hanne Oberman, Utrecht University
382 Hanne Meulenbeld, KNAW
383 Jan Willem Wijnen, Openjournals.nl
384 Roger van der Hoeven, Radboud University
385 Maud Govers, Radboud University
386 Rimma Grishmanovskaya, Tilburg University

- 387 Chiara Livio, Utrecht University
- 388 Iris Smal, University of Amsterdam
- 389 Anonymous, VU Amsterdam
- 390 Anonymous, VU Amsterdam
- 391 Justus Bogner, VU Amsterdam
- 392 Roos de Jong, VU Amsterdam
- 393 Patris van Boxel, DANS KNAW
- 394 Fleur Verbiest, VU Amsterdam
- 395 Jeroen Timmerman, University of Amsterdam
- 396 Mariëlle Beek, Perspekt & East Side
- 397 Aart van Stekelenburg, Radboud University
- 398 Anonymous, Eindhoven University
- 399 Gerlov van Engelenhoven, Leiden University
- 400 Barbara Vermaas, Fontys University of Applied Sciences
- 401 Henry van der Burgt, Radboud University
- 402 Nicole Loorbach, University of Twente
- 403 Marian Beekman, Leiden UMC
- 404 Wim Pouw, Radboud University
- 405 Bert N. Bakker, University of Amsterdam
- 406 Joppe Klein Breteler, Radboud University
- 407 Ellen Touwen, Leiden University
- 408 Andrea van Langerak, Leiden University

Link to the online petition

The online petition and up-to-date list of signatories can be found here:

<https://openscienceretreat.eu/call-to-commitment-future-proof-oa-publishing/>